

ULTRASONIC INSPECTION OF
GRAPHITE-ALUMINUM COMPOSITES*

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Graphite reinforced aluminum composites have evolved into a promising new material for many unique high performance applications. The need for assurance of sound structures has always been present and several studies have been conducted to demonstrate the applicability of existing non-destructive inspection methods to this new composite system. The present study deals with two types of tests, X-ray and ultrasonics. This study shows that normal radiographic techniques are not sensitive enough to detect typical defects in this composite and that pulse-echo techniques of ultrasonic inspection are more discerning to defects than through transmission techniques of ultrasonic inspection. The study also demonstrates the presentation of the pulse echo information in a 3-D mode by a commercially available ultrasonic inspection system is extremely useful in the determination of defect type and location.

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Introduction

The non destructive inspection of graphite-aluminum composite presents unique problems. The composite is manufactured by vapor coating tows of graphite fibers, molten infiltrating the coated tows to form a precursor wire and consolidating these wires into composite structures. Typical defects in these structures are noninfiltrated groups of fibers and incomplete bonding of wires, delaminations. The former defect is introduced during the vapor coating-molten infiltrating step of manufacture while the latter is introduced during consolidation of precursor wires.

Standard X-ray techniques are not sensitive to these defects and thus provide very little useful information for inspection of graphite-aluminum composites. Ultrasonic waves penetrate this composite easily and can provide useful inspection information. The sensitivity of the ultrasonic waves are equal to the wave length of the sound and are typically 0.018 inches for 10 MHz waves in aluminum. Two methods of processing the ultrasonic signals for inspection of the graphite-aluminum composites are considered in this study: Both methods employ one transducer which sends and receives the waves. The first method, referred to as through transmission, analyzes the reflection from the surface of a back-up plate beneath the sample. This method determines energy loss due to passage of sound through the sample. The loss of sound energy caused by any process; absorption, reflection etc., will create a defect indication. The second method, referred to as pulse-echo, analyzes the reflections which arise within the sample. The reflection of sound energy greater than a preset minimum creates a defect indication.

Each of these modes of inspection have unique problems associated with it. The pulse echo method suffers from a near surface non-inspection area that is caused by the transducer vibration after receiving the reflection from the front surface of the sample. This vib-

Fig. 1. Ultrasonic signal from front surface, flaw and back surface of test sample.

ration must be gated from the processed signal, Fig. 1. For complete inspection, the sample must be inspected from both sides. The through transmission method suffers from being sensitive to the microstructural make up of the composite. Generally, a metallurgical structure, e.g., grain size, has an effect on the ultrasonic transmissibility for all metals; the larger the grain size, the greater the attenuation. The magnitude of the effect is frequency-dependent; the higher the test frequency, the greater the attenuation of ultrasound. When the grain size, or structure size approaches 0.25 mm (0.010 inch), the effect is significant regardless of test frequency (Ref. 1). The graphite-aluminum composite, especially the Thornel 50 composites, contain several structural elements that are between 0.010 and 0.050 inch. These elements are; the individual plies of Thornel 50, 0.010 inch, areas of excess aluminum where surface foils were trapped between precursor wires, 0.010 to 0.020 inch, and original precursor wire bundles, 0.030 to 0.050 inch, Fig. 2. All of these structural elements attenuate sound, and cause ambiguous defect signals in the through transmission mode of inspection.

0.015 in.

Fig. 2. Microsection of surface region of Thornel 50-201 aluminum composite. Individual plies are 0.015 inch in diameter and the excess aluminum foil between two precursor wires is approximately 0.005 inch wide and 0.015 inch deep.

The present study involved inspection of four plates of graphite-aluminum composite using X-radiography, ultrasonic through transmission and ultrasonic pulse-echo methods. The pulse-echo inspection was conducted using a newly developed Holosonics System 200 that produces simultaneous plan and section views during inspection and has the capability to produce 3-dimensional views of defects that can be tilted and rotated for ease of interpretation. Microsections were taken from the plates in areas determined to contain defects by either ultrasonic method of inspection. These microsections demonstrated the type and size of defect that could be detected by these inspection methods.

Experimental

The four plates of graphite-aluminum composite were approximately $5\frac{1}{2}$ inch square and six plies thick. The

plates were identified as follows:

- A. T50/201 Al partially bonded with some substandard wire included to simulate non-infiltration and delaminations.
- B. T50/201 Al fully bonded with .003 inch of 2024 Al bonded at the center line.
- C. T50/201 Al 0° - 90° - 0° - 0° - 90° - 0° rebonded monolayers known to contain microcracks after bonding.
- D. HM 3000/201 Al fully bonded state-of-the-art plate.

All plates were inspected with Holosonics System with a $3/4$ inch diameter, broadband MHz transducer having a 4 inch focal length in the through transmission and pulse echo modes (2 and 3). The system 200 has a capability to produce simultaneously a plan view, C-scan, and section view, B-scan, while operating in the pulse echo mode. The section view can be either a single scan or a composite of the entire piece inspected. Both types of section views were made in this study to demonstrate the over all position of the defect indications, composite section view, and the specific location of certain defect indications, single scan section view. Plate D was also inspected by means of standard ultrasonic "C" scan techniques and by X-radiography with parameters appropriate for 0.250 inch thick aluminum (4).

After ultrasonic inspection all plates were sectioned at appropriate positions and metallographically inspected for defects that caused flaw indications. Standard polishing procedures for aluminum were used and some samples were etched with Keller's Reagent.

Results and Discussion

A detailed analysis of the inspections can be found in reference 3. Highlight will be presented in this section.

1. Plate A

Plate A was processed at a low temperature to produce a partially delaminated structure. The through-transmission and pulse-echo plan views, the pulse-echo composite section view and a photograph of the sectioned plate are shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 3. - Plan Views and Composite Section View of Plate A. a) Through-transmission plan view. b) Pulse-echo plan view. c) Photograph of section plate [light areas is defective as defined in (a)]. d) Pulse-echo composite section view.

There are several lines drawn on the pulse-echo plan view. They are identified with lower case arabic letters such as a-a and b-b. These lines correspond to the locations where single scan section views of the plate are located.

0.030 in.

0.010 in.

Figure 4. - Optical Micrograph of Plate A at Section b-b with Multiple Delaminations in Fourth Ply Determined by Pulse-Echo in Area Determined Undefective by Through Transmission Etched.

An example of the type of defect found in plate A is shown in Fig. 4.

The pulse-echo inspection demonstrated that several defects were present in this area in the third and fourth plies while the through transmission indicated a defect free area. The micrograph shows that several delaminations are present in the third and fourth plies that are approximately 0.010 inch wide.

Several general conclusions can be drawn from the inspection of Plate A: (1) Severe delaminations and combinations of delaminations and void areas can be easily detected by through-transmission inspection, in areas where severe defects are present in the gated

Figure 5. - Plan Views and Composite Section View of Plate B. a) Through-Transmission Plan View. b) Pulse-Echo Plan View. c) Photograph of Sectioned Plate. d) Pulse-Echo Composite Section View.

thickness, pulse echo inspection shows no defects. (2) Small delaminations can be missed by through-transmission yet are easily detected by pulse echo.

2. Plate B

Plate B was fabricated by means of a standard temperature-pressure-time sequence, which consistently yields high-strength plates (5). This plate was used to demonstrate the influence of the midplane foil on the ultrasonic signal. A photograph, a through-transmission plan view, pulse-echo plan view and pulse-echo composite section view of this plate are shown in Fig. 5.

The through-transmission and pulse-echo plan views have very little correspondence; the through-transmission view has a majority of defects in the upper area while

the pulse echo has a majority of defects in the lower area. The lower half of this plate was polished prior to inspection.

Figure 2 is a microsection from the area between scans b-b, and c-c, shown to be defective by through-transmission and defect free by pulse-echo. This area is approximately 0.020 inch deep and 0.020 inch wide at the top. This size of microstructural element will attenuate ultrasound and cause a defect indication in the through-transmission mode. The influence of this type of structure on the properties of the composite are not known at the present time.

Another example of the types of defects found in Plate B is shown in Fig. 6. This area was determined

Figure 6. - Optical Micrograph of Plate B at section b-b in an Area determined defect free by Through-Transmission and to contain a defect in the center by Pulse-Echo. Etched.

to be defect free by through-transmission but to contain a defect approximately at the center by pulse-echo as shown in the section view in Fig. 6. This cross section does contain an area of non-infiltration in the center that is 0.015 inch wide and 0.005 inch thick.

The inspection of Plate B indicates that through-transmission is sensitive to surface condition, a polished surface gave rise to fewer defect indications and foil rich areas caused defect indications, Fig. 2. Non-infiltrated regions up to 0.015 inch wide were not detected by through-transmission. Pulse-echo inspection can easily detect noninfiltrated areas 0.010 inch wide. The inspection of this plate also indicates that well-bonded internal foils do not cause extra reflections and do not impede the high-sensitivity inspection of material below the foils.

Figure 7. - Plan Views and Composite Section View of Plate C. a) Through-Transmission Plan View. b) Pulse-Echo Plan View. c) Photograph of Section Plate C. d) Pulse-Echo Composite Section View.

3. Plate C

Plate C was fabricated by means of a standard sequence to rebond plies of composite in a 0° - 90° - 0° orientation. The difference in thermal expansion of the composite in the 0° and 90° direction creates high stress in the composite during cooling after bonding. These stresses cause microcracking in each ply of the plate. A photograph of the sectioned plate, a through-transmission plan view, a pulse echo plan view and a composite section view of Plate C are shown in Fig. 7. There is good correspondence between the through-transmission and pulse-echo plan views of this plate in the center. The pulse-echo inspection contains more flow indications than does the through-transmission view.

Microsections from the center areas of this plate determined to be defective by both pulse-echo and through-transmission contain both cracks across the plies and delaminations. A microsection from an area determined to

Figure 8. - Optical Micrograph of Plate C at Section a-a in Area Determined Defect Free by Through-Transmission and to Have Flaws in the Third and Fourth Plies by Pulse-Echo. Unetched. (dark areas in longitudinal plies are polishing artifacts)

be defect free by through-transmission but to contain flaws in the third and fourth plies by pulse-echo is shown in Fig. 8. This area contains cracks; the cracks with the widest separation are 0.010 inch wide and extend 0.035 inch deep, the ply thickness. The inspection of Plate C indicated that with through-transmission delaminations between plies in a cross-ply configuration can be easily detected, however with 7-MHz planar waves ply cracking cannot be detected. With pulse-echo inspection, the delaminated areas as well as the areas containing ply cracks can be detected when the cracks are wider than 0.003 inch.

4. Plate D

Plate D was fabricated by means of a standard temperature-pressure-time sequence that consistently yields high-strength plates from T50/201 precursor wires (5).

Figure 9. - Plan Views and Composite Section View of Plate D. a) Through-Transmission Plan View. b) Pulse-Echo Plan View. c) Photograph of Sectional Plate D. d) Pulse-Echo Composite Section View.

A new precursor, Hercules HM 3000/201, was used for this plate. A photograph of the sectioned plate, through-transmission and pulse-echo plan views and a composite section view of Plate D are shown in Fig. 9. The sensitivity setting for the through-transmission inspections were adjusted so that Plate D would appear to be defect free. The pulse-echo inspection therefore revealed more defects than the through-transmission.

Since Plate D acted as the standard for the study, additional inspections were performed on it. A print of an X-radiograph of the plate is shown in Fig. 10. The sensitivity of the X-ray image with the 0.250 inch penetrometer block located to the left of the plate is shown; fiber orientation and the waviness of the fibers are evident. This image also clearly defined the cracks that are present in the foils on the surface. However, no information concerning bonding integrity or fiber infiltration is evident.

Figure 10. - X-radiograph of Plate D.

Figure 11. - Through-Transmission Images for "C" Scan and Plan View from System 200 at 10 MHz.

Plate D was also inspected with a sound frequency of 10 MHz with the System 200 and by means of standard "C" scan equipment (4). The images from these inspections are shown in Fig. 11. The "C" scan image represents a condition where a defect is indicated when less than 38 percent of the maximum reflected signal is received by the transducer. These two images do not agree with one another. The "C" scan indicates that the majority of the defects are found in the right side of the plate while the System 200 indicates that some defects are on the right side but the majority of the defects are on the left side, in agreement with the pulse-echo inspection, Fig. 9(a).

The most interesting inspection on this plate was conducted in the area of sections d-d and e-e, Fig. 9(a). These areas were shown to contain defects by pulse-echo and through-transmission at 10 MHz with the System 200 and section d-d was shown to contain a defect by the "C" scan when the sensitivity was increased over that

Figure 12. - Magnified 3-D Image of Defect in Sections d-d and e-e in Plate D.

shown in Fig. 11. A magnified and rotated 3-D image of this area shows that the defect is in the third ply, has two sections and is 0.360 inch long parallel to the fiber direction, Fig. 12. The optical micrographs of sections taken at d-d and e-e show that the defect is two non-infiltrated regions of one wire in the third ply, Fig. 13. Section d-d, Fig. 13(a) also contains an area of excess aluminum between wires on the lower surface. It is not clear that the through-transmission inspections did not detect this area rather than the non-infiltrated wire, however the demonstrated minimum size capability for through-transmission "C" scan inspection is approximately 0.050 inch (4).

The inspection of Plate D demonstrates that normal X-ray inspection is not capable of defining defects that are typically found in graphite-aluminum composites. "C" scan inspection carried out at 10 MHz is sensitive

0.030 in.

0.030 in.

0.010 in.

0.010 in.

(a)

(b)

Figure 13. - Optical Micrographs of Plate D at Sections of d-d (a), and e-e (b). Etched.

to surface condition and microstructural elements and produces defect indications when excess aluminum areas between wires are present. The pulse-echo inspection, especially with the three dimensional capability, is extremely sensitive to defects in the graphite-aluminum composite and is able to define non-infiltrated areas as small as 0.010 inch. This system also gives defect position and shape information not obtainable by the other inspection techniques employed.

Conclusions

The non-destructive inspection of graphite-aluminum composite can be conducted very accurately with ultrasonic pulse-echo methods. In this study, a commercial unit,

the Holosonics System 200, operating at 7 MHz defined non-infiltrated areas as small as 0.008 inch in diameter. This system also detected cracks that were parallel to the direction of sound propagation when the crack opening was >0.003 inch. This unit also simultaneously produces plan and section views of the part being inspected that are useful in determining the exact position of defects.

A unique feature of the System 200 is the ability to produce three-dimensional images of defects that can be magnified, tilted and rotated to aid in the identification of defects. This type of image was used to detect two 0.010 inch non-infiltrated regions in a wire that were separated by 0.030 inch.

Through-transmission inspection gives information about the integrity of the composite on a coarser level. Conventional ultrasonics "C" scan inspection conducted at 10 MHz may have detected non-infiltrated regions that were 0.020 inch in diameter, however microstructural elements 0.025 inch in diameter were also present in these areas and many have also caused the signals. The "C" scan produced many defect indications in nonuniform microstructural areas such as surface irregularities and foil nonuniformities. Signals from significant flaws cannot be separated from irrelevant ones, thus limiting the usefulness of conventional through-transmission inspection for graphite-aluminum composites.

Conventional X-ray inspection clearly reveals cracks in surface foils but fails to detect areas of non-infiltration. This inspection technique is very limited for finding defects in graphite-aluminum composites.

References

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